

MANAGEMENT OF LIFESTYLE DISORDER THROUGH AHARA WSR TO STHOLYA (OBESITY)

***Dr. Jhilima Behera**

2nd Year MD Scholar of Kayachikitsa Department, Gopabandhu Ayurveda Mahavidyalya,
Puri, Odisha.

Article Received on 20 October 2025,
Article Revised on 10 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Nov. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17616266>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Jhilima Behera

2nd Year MD Scholar of Kayachikitsa
Department, Gopabandhu Ayurveda
Mahavidyalya, Puri, Odisha.

How to cite this Article: *Dr. Jhilima Behera
(2025) Management Of Lifestyle Disorder
Through Ahara Wsr To Stholya (Obesity).
"World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research,
14(22), 534-539.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The aim of Ayurveda is to promote & preserve the health, strength & longevity of the healthy person (swastika) & cure the disease. In present era Diet & lifestyle are major factor to produce many disorders like Diabetes, cancerous disease, Hormonal imbalance (menarche in early age) etc. Ayurveda places special emphasis on Ahara & believes that healthy nutrition nourishes the mind, body & soul. Ahara considered as one of the key pillars (upastambha) of life in Ayurveda. Today's world, altered habits of food consumption may leads to various disease, so many guidelines explained in Ayurvedic text, which are titled on AharaVidhi, pathyaApathya Ahara, what occurs when intake of virudhha Ahara (incompatible food), lifestyle disorders due to Apathya Ahara. In Ayurveda text also explained that if a patient intake pathya Ahara then no need to intake medicines & also if a patient not intake Pathya

Ahara, then medicines also can't cures the diseases, So Diet according to diseases has greatest importance to cure diseases. Ayurveda suggest that one should follow guiding principles to prevent various diseases.

KEYWORDS: AharaVidhi, Pathya Apathya Ahara, lifestyle disorders, how to prevent diseases due to intake of Ahara WSR to Stholya (Obesity).

INTRODUCTION

Ahara is an important factor in all system of medicine. Ayurveda has different approach in the

& kapha dosha predominant so avoided the vataja, kaphajaahara.

- 5) **Kala:** (Time period) – Nityag kala – Ahara which is taken as per day, night & ritu. Avasthika kala – Ahara taken as per Specific disease.
- 6) **Upayokta:** Upayokta is the person who takes food. The action of food depends on the psychological & physical attitude of the person.
- 7) **Upayogasamstha:** This stands for the dietetic rules. These are important for proper digestion.

If food is taken by rules. food is properly digested. otherwise there may be ama formation which leads to disease formation which is one of the major cause of many disease formation.

Pathyapathya Ahara

Ahara one which is not harmful for our body and one which is pleasant to our mind is pathya, this is always recommended, and one which is harmful both for body & mind is not recommended and hence called as Apathya. but according to matra, kala, kriya, bhumi, desha, doshas pathyadravya turned into Apathya, so pathya ahara should taken as per matra, kala, kriya, bhumi, desha, doshas.

Life style disorder WSR to obesity through Ahara:- Life style disorder mainly result from the factors like unhealthy diet. bad food habits, lack of physical activity etc. Acharya carak explained Atisthula (obese) under the asthaninditapurusha.

Pathogenesis: The increases kapha pradhana tridosha & medadhatu obstruct the entire channels (srotas) which in turn causes vata aggrevation, that is responsible for stimulating the fire, so food get digested quickly and appetite increases therefore patients eats frequently. Due to fat deposition in Udara (abdomen), nitamba (buttocks), stanapradesha (breast) loose their normal shape & contour & become flobby & pendulous.

- Modern science also explained due to over nutrition & dietary imbalance may lead to disease like obesity. Obesity is associated with increased adipose store in the subcutaneous tissue, skeletal muscles. Internal organs such the kidneys, heart, liver & omentum, fatty liver is also more common in obese individual. There is increase in both size & number of adipocytes, there is hypertrophy as well as hyperplasia.
- **Metabolic changes** –1) Hyper insulinaemia– Increase insulin secretion is a feature of obesity. Many obese patients exhibit hyperglycaemia or frank diabetes.

- 2) Non – insulin dependent diabetes –There is a strong association of non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus with obesity.
- 3) Hypertension –Due to obesity increased blood volume leads to hypertension.
- 4) Hyperlipoproteinaemia – The plasma cholesterol circulates in the blood as low density lipoprotein (LDL) containing most of the circulating triglycerides. Obesity is strongly associated with VLDL & mildly with LDL total blood cholesterol levels are also elevated in obesity.
- 5) Atherosclerosis– Obesity predisposes to development of Atherosclerosis.
- 6) Coronary artery disease & Stroke –As a result of atherosclerosis & hypertension there is increased risk of Myocardial infarction & Stroke in obese individual.
- 7) Cholelithiasis–There is six times higher incidence of gall stones in obese persons mainly due to increased total body cholesterol.
- 8) Hypoventilation syndrome – During at night & day in obese individual along with carbon dioxide retention, hypoxia, polycythemia.
- 9) Osteoarthritis –Due to large body weight individual are more prone to develop degenerative joint disease because lack of movement.
- 10) Cancer –In present era. intake of improper diet is the major cause for cancerous diseases. such as endometrium & breast seen to be related to obesity

How to prevent Stholya (obesity) due to intake of ahara

- According to Charak Samhita Guru bhojan and Apatarpana chikitsa should be done because in Atistholya purusha jatharagni is tikshna so Guru bhojan should be given but which is apatarpana (shosana) in nature means which reduce medadhatu. (Ca. Su 21/20)
- According to Astanga hridaya Chikitsa should be done by ahara which is reduce medadhatu, vatadosha and kaphadosha. such as kulathi, yava, Mudga, madhu mixed with water, kanji, asaba, arista, sodhana (vamana, virechana) should be taken. In Ayurveda Sashtra Nidanaparivarjana should be done first. (A.H.Su 14/ 20)
- According to Acharya Susruta Atistolya chikitsa–Sudhhasilajit, Sudhhaguggulu, Gomutra, Madhu, yava, muga, koradushaka (kododhana), chhedaniya dravya should be taken as per rule & exercises should be done. (Su. Su 15/38).

DISCUSSION

In present era Diet & lifestyle are major factor to produce many lifestyle disorder mostly atistolya (obesity) related disorder. Taking food in irregular quantity, improper time & also

taking more quantity of junk food disrupts normal digestion process which is rich in fat & fibers. Adhyasana (food intake after indigestion of food), Visamasana (intake both pathya & Apathya ahara at a time). Stholya is the nearest clinical entity for ayurveda, for causation of stholya, excessive intake of kaphayukta ahara. In ayurveda obese person are included under astanindita purusha. The reason for difficult nature being the involvement of tridosha and affliction of saptadhatu. If a person follows the rule of pathya for particular disease, there is very little significance of drug treatment. Ayurvedic science explained for most of the diseases Ahara plays an important role as that of medicine, especially disease like stholya. hence it is rightly mentioned that “if one follow pathya then there is no need of medicine & if not there is no use of therapeutic measures “Acharya Charak has stressed upon the use of Guru & Aparpana as a special regimen for stholya. Ahara dravya should be used after converting it to guru through samskara. Ausadhasevana alone can not alleviate the disease if defective food habits are practice. On other hand. if appropriate food habits acting as pathya is included in daily regimen even Ausadhasevana can be reduced or prevented. Hence Aharadravyas which are recommended as pathya for stholya(obese) can be advised to be included in regular diet form of preparation such as kulathha. chanaka in the form of yusha. sunthi in the form of sunthijala. takra. adraka. Vegetables like potala, karavelaka. shigru will bring about effect. Ayurveda also recommended that warm water is good for digestive health. Thus warm water has medicinal properties like kaphahara, dilatation properties etc.

CONCLUSION

Ahara plays a major role in swasthya Rakshana. By its nature of pathya & Apathya ahara can become Nidana(causative factor) for both health & sickness. Hence following appropriate pathya & avoiding Apathya leads to better health in case of Stholya.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita sutra sthana chapter 25 sloka 40 vol 1 Chaukhambabharati Academi, Varanasi.
2. Kasyapa Samhita khilasthana chapter 5 sloka9.
3. Agnivesha Charaka Samhita Sutra sthana chapter28 sloka 45 vol 1 Chaukhambabharati Academy, varanasi.
4. Agnivesha Charaka Samhita VimanaSthanachapter 2 sloka 3 vol 1 chaukhamababharati Academy, varanasi.
5. Vagbhata AstangaHridayamSutra sthana chapter 8 sloka 1 Chaukhamba Sanskrit

- pratisthana, Delhi.
6. Agnivesha Charaka Samhita VimanSthana Chapter 1 sloka 21 Vol 1
Chaukhambabharati Academy Varanasi.
 7. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita VimanSthanachapter 1 sloka 24 vol 1
Chaukhambabharati Academy Varanasi.
 8. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita Sutra sthana chapter 25 sloka 45. 46 Vol 1
Chaukhambabharati Academy Varanasi.
 9. Agnivesha, Charak Samhita Sutra sthana chapter 21 sloka 3,5- 9 vol 1
chaukhambabharati Academ. Varanasi.
 10. Vagbhata, Astangahridayam Sutra sthana chapter 11 sloka10.11 chaukhamba Sanskrit
pratisthana, Delhi.
 11. Sushruta, SushrutaSamhita Sutra sthana chapter 15 sloka11 Vol 1 chaukhamba
Sanskrit Samsthana, Varanasi.
 12. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita sutra sthana chapter 15 sloka37 vol 1 chaukhambha
Sanskrit Samsthana, Varansi.
 13. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita Sutra sthana chapter 21 sloka20 vol 1
Chaukhambabharati Academy, Varanasi.
 14. Vagbhata, Astangahridayam sutra sthana chapter 14 sloka32 Chaukhamba Sanskrit
Pratisthana, Varanasi.
 15. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita Sutra sthana chapter 15 sloka 38 Vol 1 chaukhamba
Sanskrit Samsthana, Varanasi.
 16. International Ayurvedic Medical Journal ISSN 23205091